

Release of Phosphorus from Iron and Aluminium Phosphates by Ion-exchange Technique

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Freshly prepared and digested forms of aluminium and ferric phosphates were mixed with an acid Ranchi soil, a neutral Madhubani soil and a calcareous Samastipur soil, and the mixtures were kept in contact with an anion-exchange resin contained in a cellophane bag under waterlogged conditions. The phosphorus uptake by the resin was determined as a function of time. The values of phosphorus release from ferric and aluminium phosphates of the soils of different locations were compared along with the pH values.

INORGANIC phosphates constitute the major source of phosphorus in soils which is utilised by the plants. However, inorganic phosphates undergo anion-exchange reactions with soil components and clay minerals, exchanging with OH^- , Fe^- , SiO_3^{2-} , AsO_4^{3-} and possibly other anions^{1,2}. The ion-exchange behaviour of soil components/clay minerals with respect to phosphate ions have been extensively investigated by several workers over a long period of time³⁻⁹. Anion-exchange resins have been used by some workers to setup models to simulate the behaviour of plant roots in taking up nutrients, e.g. phosphorus, from soils¹⁰⁻¹².

However, plant roots can take up phosphate only in a solution form and the rate of dissolution of a solid phosphate may be higher than the rate of phosphorus uptake by plant roots¹³. In this context, the solubility behaviour of solid phosphates vis-a-vis ion-exchange behaviour, hopefully simulating root-soil systems, can be rewarding for a better understanding of optimum phosphate fertiliser applications. The present work was undertaken with this aim in view.

Experimental

Soil samples of Ranchi, Madhubani and Samastipur districts (all in Bihar State) were collected, air-dried, ground and passed through a 0.5 mm sieve. The analytical characteristics of these soils are given in Table 1.

Freshly prepared and digested forms of ferric and aluminium phosphates were mixed with the soil (100 g) in 250 ml glass beakers in a proportion to ensure that each beaker contained 100 ppm of

Parameter	Acid soil (Ranchi)	Neutral soil (Madhubani)	Calcareous soil (Samastipur)
pH (1 : 2)	4.7	7.1	8.2
E. Conductivity ($\text{m } \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	0.20	0.90	0.85
Organic carbon (%)	0.86	0.55	0.26
C.E.C. (me/100 g)	7.1	22.8	17.9
Available-P (ppm) (Morgan's extract)	3.8	52.2	3.2
Total-P (ppm) (HCl extract)	160	320	520
Total FeIII (%) (HCl extract)	0.77	0.46	0.41
Free CaCO_3 (%)	—	—	34.5
Coarse sand (%)	43.9	2.2	2.0
Fine sand (%)	26.5	52.4	64.2
Silt (%)	14.7	32.7	15.7
Clay (%)	14.6	13.0	17.8

phosphorus/100 g of soil. The treated samples were incubated at room temperature ($28 \pm 2^\circ$) under waterlogged conditions. The water level was maintained at 6 cm above the soil surface and any evaporated water was replenished as required. Two drops of toluene was added in each beaker to arrest fungal growth.

Indion (FFIP) strong base anion-exchange resin was converted to the hydroxyl form, washed with distilled water and air-dried. The resin (5 g) along with distilled water (15 ml) were taken in cellophane bags suspended in the beakers containing the soil-fertilisers mixtures. The resin bags suspended in different beakers containing soil-fertiliser mixtures were removed after 10, 20, 30, 60 and 90 day periods, and pH of the soil-fertiliser mixtures were

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recorded using a pH meter. The contents of the resin bags were then equilibrated with 0.5 N hydrochloric acid (50 ml) in 250 ml beakers for 1 h²⁴ and the supernatant liquids were decanted into 100 ml volumetric flasks and the phosphorus content was determined¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 gives the initial and final pH of the soil – fertiliser mixtures at the end of 90-day treatment with the anion-exchange resin and the total phosphorus exchanged after this treatment for the three different soils mixed with freshly prepared and digested forms of aluminium and ferric phosphates. Figs. 1 and 2 give the phosphorus release (ppm) as a function of time for the three soils treated with

freshly prepared and digested forms of aluminium phosphate and Figs. 3 and 4 give the corresponding data for the ferric phosphate treated soils. In all these soils, the freshly prepared fertilisers show a larger amount of phosphorus release compared to the digested forms, evidently due to their higher solubility¹⁶.

Figs. 1 and 3 show that freshly prepared fertilisers released the maximum amount of phosphorus at the incubation period of 20 days, after which the phosphorus release decreased in all the soils. But in the neutral Madhubani soil, a second phosphorus release peak is noted at 60-day incubation period.

Figs. 2 and 4 show that the digested forms of aluminium and ferric phosphate behaved differently in different soils. In the acid Ranchi soil, the rate of phosphorus release is comparable for both the fertilisers treatment and is very low upto 60-day incubation, but increases considerably at 90-day incubation. In the neutral Madhubani soil, the

TABLE 2—RELEASE OF PHOSPHORUS FROM DIFFERENT FORMS OF ALUMINIUM AND FERRIC PHOSPHATES IN SOILS UNDER SIMULATED CONDITIONS OF SOIL-PLANT SYSTEM

Soil	Treatment*	pH		Amount of P exchange in five successive process (ppm)
		Initial 0 day	Final 90 day	
Ranchi	AlP(F)	5.07	6.98	28.5
	AlP(D)	5.70	6.92	2.8
	FeP(F)	5.35	6.91	26.1
	FeP(D)	5.84	6.96	2.5
Madhubani	AlP(F)	6.98	7.21	34.2
	AlP(D)	7.43	7.53	8.5
	FeP(F)	7.16	7.26	30.7
	FeP(D)	7.47	7.56	3.8
Samastipur	AlP(F)	8.10	7.27	34.4
	AlP(D)	8.62	7.52	1.7
	FeP(F)	7.97	7.26	38.8
	FeP(D)	8.45	7.50	18.7

*AlP(F)=Freshly prepared aluminium phosphate, AlP(D)=digested aluminium phosphate, FeP(F)=freshly prepared ferric phosphate, FeP(D)=digested ferric phosphate.

Fig. 1. Release of phosphorus from freshly prepared aluminium phosphate: (O) Ranchi soil, (Δ) Madhubani soil and (□) Samastipur soil.

Fig. 2. Release of phosphorus from digested aluminium phosphate: (O) Ranchi soil, (Δ) Madhubani soil and (□) Samastipur soil.

largest amount of phosphorus has been released after 10 days, followed by a sharp decrease after 20 days. A sharp increase upto 30 days and gradually beyond that is observed again. The amount of phosphorus is more for aluminium phosphate than for ferric phosphate. In the calcareous Samastipur soil, the behaviour of aluminium phosphate is comparable with that of the acid Ranchi soil, but there is an initial decrease in phosphorus release at the 20-day incubation period and phosphorus release rate beyond 60 days is much lower compared to the Ranchi soil. With ferric phosphate, however, there is a sharp initial increase in phosphorus release upto 30-day incubation followed by a sharp fall.

Along with phosphorus exchange, pH of the soil – fertiliser system also changes (Table 2). In

Fig. 3. Release of phosphorus from freshly prepared ferric phosphate: (O) Ranchi soil, (Δ) Madhubani soil and (□) Samastipur soil.

Fig. 4. Release of phosphorus from digested ferric phosphate: (O) Ranchi soil, (Δ) Madhubani soil and (□) Samastipur soil.

acid soil, pH increases to neutrality (6.83–6.94)¹⁷, whereas in neutral and calcareous soils, pH decreases, stabilising in the range¹⁸ 7.45–7.56.

Table 3 gives the effect of Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃ and CaCO₃ additions on the phosphorus availability of aluminium and ferric phosphate, as determined from our analysis, under submerged conditions. The phosphorus availability from ferric phosphate decreases in presence of Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃ and CaCO₃.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃ AND CaCO₃ ON PHOSPHORUS AVAILABILITY OF FERRIC AND ALUMINIUM PHOSPHATES UNDER SUBMERGED CONDITIONS

Fertilisers	Available P (% of total P)			
	Control	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	CaCO ₃
Ferric phosphate	0.76	0.24	0.32	0.38
Aluminium phosphate	0.34	0.40	0.32	0.10

and the largest decrease is observed in presence of Fe₂O₃ (68%), followed by Al₂O₃ (~52%) and CaCO₃ (50%). The phosphorus availability from aluminium phosphate increases in presence of Fe₂O₃ (15%), and decreases slightly in presence of Al₂O₃ (~6%). A sharp decrease in presence of CaCO₃ (~71%) is however observed.

The effect of pH on phosphorus solubility (% of total phosphorus) for aluminium and ferric phosphates is shown in Fig. 5. The solubility of ferric phosphate increases sharply beyond pH 8, while that of aluminium phosphate shows an initial decrease at pH 4–5 and a sharp increase beyond pH 8. Beyond pH 5, the solubility of ferric phosphate is higher than that of aluminium phosphate.

in presence of metal oxides/carbonates and phosphorus solubility at different pH can help to understand the patterns shown in Table 2 and Figs. 1–4.

Table 1 reveals that both the calcareous Samastipur soil and the neutral Madhubani soil have high total phosphorus. But the available phosphorus in Madhubani soil (~16% of the total P) is much higher than that of the other two soils (~0.6% for Samastipur and ~2% for Ranchi soil). In Figs. 1 and 3, Ranchi and Samastipur soils show comparable high phosphorus release at the first peak, but the Madhubani soil shows a second peak at 60 days which is not shown by the other two soils.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on dissolution of digested aluminium and ferric phosphates: (O) aluminium phosphate and (Δ) ferric phosphate.

In terms of cumulative phosphorus release, however, the Madhubani and Samastipur soils show comparable behaviour (Table 2). In presence of CaCO_3 , ferric phosphate releases the highest amount of phosphorus, while in presence of Fe_2O_3 , aluminium phosphate releases the highest amount of phosphorus, but not in presence of CaCO_3 (Table 3). Table 2 and Figs. 3 and 4 indicate that Samastipur soil contains higher percentage of CaCO_3 compared to the Madhubani soil, the latter however has the highest available phosphorus.

Highest phosphorus release, consistent with the highest available phosphorus in Madhubani soil is indicated for digested aluminium phosphate treated soils (Fig. 2). However, for digested ferric phosphate treated soils, the highest phosphorus release is shown by the Samastipur soil (Fig. 4). For both aluminium and ferric phosphate, the soluble phosphorus increases at pH beyond 7 (Fig. 5), hence Samastipur soil should be most effective in releasing soluble phosphorus from both the fertilisers. This seems not to be the case for aluminium phosphate, but becomes quite evident for ferric phosphate. It can be seen from Table 3 that the presence of CaCO_3 (34.5% in Samastipur soil, but negligible in Madhubani soil) significantly decreases available phosphorus from aluminium phosphate (~71%) compared to that in ferric phosphate. This is consistent with the pattern shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

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